

THE ROLE OF DIRECT METHOD IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION: In today's world, teachers can use various methods, including the Direct Method, the Audio-lingual Method, the Grammar Translation Method in their language teaching process in order to give information and attract learners' attention to the lesson and explain themes. One of the most important methods is the direct method which the target language is taught with the help of introducing experience, expressions, words, pictures, real materials and performances without using learners' mother tongue. The preference of this method is that it improves speaking, listening, reading and writing skills simultaneously because of the usage of the sufficient technics.

Keywords: the Direct Method, target language, native language, the Natural Method

INTRODUCTION. Nowadays many teachers prefer to introduce new methods for Foreign Language Teaching to their students than traditional ones. One of them is the Direct Method. It was started in France and Germany around 1900 and replaced Grammar Translation Method and other traditional methods and approaches. It became widely known in the United States through its use by

Sauveur and Maximilian Berlitz in successful commercial schools. In practice it stood for the following principles and procedures:

1. Classroom instruction was conducted exclusively in the target language.
2. Only everyday vocabulary and sentences were taught.
3. Oral communication skills were built up in a carefully graded progression organized around question-and-answer exchanges between teachers and students in small, intensive classes.
4. Grammar was taught inductively.
5. New teaching points were introduced orally.
6. Concrete vocabulary was taught through demonstration, objects, and pictures; abstract was taught by association of ideas.
7. Both speech and listening comprehension were taught.
8. Correct pronunciation and grammar were emphasized.

What is the Direct Method?

The Direct Method is connected directly with target language without learners' native language. It is also called the Natural Method that is very popular which enables the students to do a particular thing which give the opportunity to the students to communicate with someone you share or exchange information with them in foreign language which consist of a set of sounds or written symbols. Its aim is to improve the learners' communication. Instead of translating materials, teacher can teach actively through action and demonstration. In other words, the teacher is expected to use real-life materials such as pictures and toys which means that young learners can understand and imagine it without any difficulties.

Main Focus of Direct Method

In Direct Method, spoken word was given primacy. The students were taught in target language. Instruction material was presented orally with help of actions and pictures instead of printed form. Learners were not allowed to use

mother/native language to learn target language. The most important aspect of language learning in Direct Method was the practice of culture in true sense.

Advantages of Direct Method

1. Power of the gestures and expression.
2. Interest in English language and relationship in meaning and words.
3. Involve all the people engaged in an activity
4. Direct Method can depend low to high class of employees.

Disadvantages of Direct method

1. Ignore the systematic written work that is done to a fixed plan in a through and efficient way.
2. Direct Method is so much expensive because that affect upon the aids which are high cost
 1. aids.
 2. That method is helpful in early stage. It is not doing a good work in the higher classes.

Guideline for Teaching oral Language

1. Not speak the fast.
2. Not speak the slow.
3. Not speak the loudly.
4. Never irritated.
5. No use of the books.
6. Never speak the only single word

This method emphasizes on:

- oral interaction;
- spontaneous use of language;

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- no translation;
- little if any analysis of grammatical rules and structures.

CONCLUSION. Teachers should always create an atmosphere for their students to speak freely in classroom. In that way, the Direct Method can open the door for communication. Moreover, acquisition of a skill or a particular type of a knowledge acquires the process of learning which based on method. The Direct Method is considered as the most effective method in Foreign Teaching Language. That is why this method can lead to great ways for progressing students' speaking, listening, reading and writing skills simultaneously.

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